

PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF ACQUISITION AND USE OF PRINCIPLES AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN MARRIAGE

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Abstract: In this article, ways to improve communicative competence in the study of the topic "Using the basics and their importance in life" in high school chemistry classes with the help of interactive methods and ICT tools are presented.

Key words: Pedagogical technologies, basics, use of basics, properties of basics, importance of basics in life, "Who connects with chemistry", "FSMU", "KKK", PISA.

It is known that laboratory and practical exercises have an important place in the strengthening of theoretical knowledge for chemistry. Explaining laboratory and practical lessons in chemistry to students using a virtual image (animated image) on the basis of modern pedagogical technology with the help of a computer gives a good result.

It consists of innovative pedagogical technologies that educate students and develop them, as well as optimal selection of interactive methods.

What should a modern pedagogue be like?

- o To be aware of information and communication technologies;
- o Dealing with students based on their psychological characteristics;
- o Skilled actor,;
- o Orator;
- o Has deep knowledge of his subject;

o To be able to use modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods in the lessons, to be interested in foreign languages based on the requirements of the times;

o To increase their interest in science by using exhibition, handout, and multimedia tools in teaching a new subject;

o Providing information from other sources (books, internet), not limited to textbooks;

o It is necessary to educate in the spirit of national pride, humanitarianism, love for mother nature, and to teach students to apply the knowledge they have acquired in life, to be able to direct them to the profession. (4.28-b)

In this, especially, the game activity of students acquires great importance in acquiring new knowledge, forming and developing skills in them, and in general, increasing the efficiency of the process of learning chemistry.

Telling students about some substances and ingredients in foreign languages greatly increases their worldview and interest in the topic. Conducting educational processes in interactive ways has a positive effect on the effectiveness of teaching. In the process of explaining a new topic, through the "FSMU" (State your opinion, Give a reason, Give an example, Summarize) method, the free opinion of students is listened to, their medical knowledge, and their relationship to a healthy lifestyle are focused on.

I. Express your opinion:

- metal atom and hydroxyl group are bases
- bases are divided into three groups
- contain water-soluble bases
- are amphoteric and water-insoluble bases
- the famous neutralization reaction results from the action of bases and acids

II. Give a reason:

- there are bases that are widely used in life
- Sodium hydroxide is used in the production of soap, paper and synthetic fiber
- Calcium hydroxide is used in the production of polishing powder.
- Calcium hydroxide is also used to clean sulfur dioxide from exhaust gas present in power plants and factories.[5]

III. Give an example:

- Ca (OH)₂ is slaked lime
- Na(OH)CO₃ soda is prepared
- Softeners for bread and bakery products are produced

IV. Summarize.

-Sodium bicarbonate (or sodium hydrogen carbonate) is used in cooking, in the preparation of baking powders, as an antacid for treating stomach problems, and as baking soda in caustic soda.

-Ammonium hydroxide is used to clean oil stains on clothes.

Each couple can join FSMU and share their thoughts with one or more pieces of information.

When pairs of students rise to the second place, it's on the screen for everyone

The questions on PISA studies were shown to the students, and the free opinions of the students were listened to. (Appendix 6)

KKK method. This method allows students to assess their level of knowledge on certain topics.

I know I want to know I found out

I know	I want to know	I am know

2 minutes are given to write the chemical formulas of the bases. The teacher fills in the mistakes and shortcomings of the students in time.

The method "Who Connects with Chemistry".

This method mainly serves the following three purposes:

1. to increase the creativity of students, comprehensively and impartially assess the knowledge, skills and qualifications of chemistry without struggling with life;
2. to determine the possibilities of developing students' knowledge, skills and abilities;
3. formation of a future plan (targeted program) that serves to develop students' knowledge, skills and abilities. [3.112-p].

To sum up, increasing the quality and effectiveness of education, creating an opportunity for students to acquire independent and excellent knowledge, expanding their worldview and imagination, and developing their thinking skills are important for the intellectual potential of the teacher, advanced pedagogy in the course of the lesson. depends on appropriate and efficient use of technologies. Therefore, for successful education, pedagogues - teachers must be masters of their profession, dedicated. In this sense, today's teacher is required to form a person who thinks in a new way for the future of our country, looks at tomorrow with a new look, and is in tune with the times.

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